

CERTIFICATION OF ENROLLMENT

Study title: Caratteristiche cliniche, trattamento ed outcomes delle infezioni da patogeni multi- resistenti in Italia: studio osservazionale multicentrico RESISTIMIT

EudraCT Number:

(hereinafter referred to as "Study")

Promoter: Azienda Ospedaliero Universitaria Pisana

(hereinafter referred to as "Promoter")

The Promoter of the Study here declares that the Centre IRCCS ISMETT has screened in total N° patients, in particular N° 38 in 2025.

Date, 27/05/2026

Name: Prof. Marco Falcone

Signature on behalf of the Promoter

AZIENDA OSPEDALIERO UNIVERSITARIA PISANA
U.O. MALATTIE INFETTIVE
Dr. Marco Falcone